

The factors controlling marine low clouds Across Multiple Timescales

by

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Abstract

Marine low clouds are effective at cooling the Earth's surface by reflecting solar radiation. Existing research suggests that the uncertainty surrounding low cloud feedback in subtropical and extratropical regions is crucial to understanding the model spread in Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS). Previous studies showed that the seasonal variations of marine low clouds in relation to surface temperature are indicative of long-term low cloud feedback. However, controversies exist for the inference of ECS based on observed seasonal cycle of low clouds, as the exact definitions of low clouds are inconsistent across different studies. In this study, we classify marine low clouds into various types and examine their sensitivity to various cloud-controlling factors (CCFs) across seasonal, interannual timescales in models and observations. First, we separate low clouds into three regimes based on cloud top height: 1) the lower boundary layer cloud with cloud top capped at 850 hPa (LBC), 2) the upper boundary layer cloud with cloud top between 850 and 700 hPa (UBC), and 3) the multi-layer cloud with cloud top above 700 hPa (MLC). This cloud classification framework provides a robust resolution to previously contentious debates regarding subtropical low-cloud seasonality. Furthermore, it provides a unified mechanistic basis for interpreting how different types of clouds, which respond to different cloud controlling factors across multiple timescales, lead to inter-model spread.

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This is to certify that I have examined the above MPhil thesis
and have found that it is complete and satisfactory in all respects,
and that any and all revisions required by
the thesis examination committee have been made.

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1 Introduction

Accurate estimates of global temperature rise in response to increasing greenhouse gases (GHGs) are essential for effective climate change mitigation and adaptation policies. Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) is a critical metric in climate science, quantifying the change in global-mean surface temperature following a doubling of atmospheric CO₂ from the pre-industrial level. However, the range of ECS estimates derived from global climate models (GCMs) has remained persistently wide, approximately 1.5-4.5 K, for about four decades (Charney et al., 1979; Meehl et al., 2020). Recent GCMs from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) have produced an even broader range in ECS, spanning from 1.8-5.6 K with a notable increase in the mean and highest ECS values (Zelinka et al., 2020). This underscores the urgent need to understand the physical processes governing ECS and the inter-model differences in ECS.

Past studies have highlighted cloud feedback as a major factor contributing to the variability in ECS across climate models (e.g., Cess et al., 1990; Sherwood et al., 2020; Stephens, 2005). This variability arises from the complex radiative impacts of clouds on the Earth's climate system, where their representation in GCMs often falls short. Clouds have a dual role: they trap longwave radiation from the Earth's surface, resulting in a warming effect, while simultaneously reflecting incoming solar radiation, causing cooling. The net cloud radiative effect (CRE) hinges on factors such as cloud top height (CTH), cloud optical thickness (COT), cloud phase (water droplets or ice particles), and total cloud cover. As the climate warms, changes in these cloud properties can either amplify or mitigate the warming associated with rising greenhouse gases. GCMs struggle with uncertainties in cloud processes, which are not always well-understood or resolved at a given model grid size. Consequently, different GCMs yield distinct

responses in CREs to external forcings, contributing to disparities in ECS estimates. Research has revealed a strong correlation between shortwave low cloud feedback and ECS, where more positive low cloud feedback corresponds to a higher ECS (e.g., Andrews et al., 2012; Bony & Dufresne, 2005; Zelinka et al., 2020). Here, “low clouds” refer to those situated within approximately 3 km (about 680 hPa in pressure) above the Earth's surface. Typically, they exhibit substantial negative net CREs (radiative cooling). Any reduction in low cloud fraction (amount feedback) or COT (scattering feedback) can significantly perturb net radiative fluxes at the top of atmosphere (TOA), consequently impacting surface temperature.

Geographically, both subtropical (0-30°N/S) and extratropical (30-60°N/S) low clouds play significant roles in total cloud feedback (e.g., Gettelman & Sherwood, 2016; Klein et al., 2017; Sherwood et al., 2020). While extensive research on subtropical low clouds has been conducted (e.g., Bony & Dufresne, 2005), the importance of extratropical low cloud feedback has emerged more recently. Studies have revealed that the misrepresentation of mixed-phase clouds in the extratropics under global warming can lead to a significant overestimation of negative cloud phase feedback, resulting in lower ECS estimates (Frey & Kay, 2018; Tan et al., 2016). Zelinka et al. (2020) identified the enhanced positive low cloud feedback in the extratropics (30-60°N/S) as the primary factor behind the upward shift in ECS values from CMIP5 to CMIP6. Recently, Jiang et al. (2023) demonstrated that the extratropical low cloud amount feedback under long-term warming is highly correlated ($R=0.86$) with the seasonal variation of extratropical low cloud fraction (ELCF) in the present-day climate. Models with ECS values greater than 4.75 K (high ECS models) show a stronger reduction in ELCF from winter to summer, aligning more closely with the joint space-borne radar and lidar observations from CloudSat and CALIPSO, compared to models with ECS values lower than 3.3 K (low ECS models) which simulate a weaker or oppositely

phased seasonal cycle. Furtado et al. (2023) also linked seasonal variations of low clouds over the extratropical oceans, particularly the Northwest Pacific Oyashio region (139–191°E, 42–54°N), to global long-term cloud feedback. However, their analysis of the perturbed physics experiments (PPEs) using the UK Met Office Hadley Centre's climate model (HadGEM3) suggested that the experiments tend to exhibit stronger negative feedback in mid-latitudes and stronger positive feedback in the subtropical stratocumulus region when simulating stronger seasonal variations in low clouds. This complicates our understanding of the relationship between ECS estimates and low cloud feedback as inferred from seasonal variations in ELCF. Jiang et al. (2023) proposed that extratropical cyclones are primarily responsible for the seasonal variations of ELCF in high ECS models, while Furtado et al. (2023) focused on the role of estimated inversion strength (EIS) in controlling ELCF. The apparent discrepancies between Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023) motivate further investigation into the mechanisms governing the seasonal cycle of extratropical low clouds and its relationship with long-term cloud feedback and ECS.

In this study, we classify marine low clouds into various types and examine their sensitivity to various cloud controlling factors (CCFs) on seasonal, interannual and long-term changes in models and observations. We separate low clouds into three regimes based on cloud top height: 1) the lower boundary layer cloud (LBC) with cloud top capped at 850 hPa, 2) the upper boundary layer cloud (UBC) with cloud top between 850 and 700 hPa, and 3) the multi-layer cloud (MLC) with cloud top above 700 hPa, using CESM2 model simulations that output data every 6 hours to resolve diurnal variations. To better understand how different types of low clouds play a role in ECS, we also examine three types of low cloud in other climate model with a daily output. To validate our assumption, CloudSat-CALIPSO and ERA5 reanalysis data are used to calculate how sensitive the three types of low clouds are to different CCFs on seasonal and inter-annual time scale. Using our classification framework, we effectively resolve

seasonal cycle discrepancies in low-cloud regimes identified by Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023). Besides, this study also provides insights to understand the physical mechanisms controlling different types of clouds. We implement the CCF framework to analyze seasonal and inter-annual variations across three cloud regimes.

2 Model and Methods

2.1 AMIP Model

The atmospheric simulations were conducted using the Community Atmosphere Model version 6 (CAM6), the atmospheric component of the Community Earth System Model version 2.1.5 (CESM2), developed at the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), which is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) (Bogenschutz et al., 2018; Gettelman et al., 2018). For this study, CAM6 was the latest supported release, integrating enhanced atmospheric physics parameterizations, cloud microphysical processes, and boundary layer turbulence treatments, all implemented through a finite-volume (FV) dynamical framework.

The model was run following the Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project (AMIP) protocols, prescribed with observational sea surface temperatures and sea ice coverage from 1979 to 2014 (Huang et al., 2021; Rayner et al., 2003). Monthly boundary condition data were linearly interpolated in time to generate daily forcing inputs. The modeling framework was also forced with temporally evolving aerosol emissions and greenhouse gas concentrations (including CO₂) to maintain fidelity with historical atmospheric composition.

The numerical experiments adopted the standard CAM6 scientific resolution: the horizontal discretization featured a 0.94° latitude × 1.25° longitude grid, while the vertical structure employed 32 hybrid sigma-pressure layers extending to 2.26 hPa.

Output datasets encompassed both static and dynamic prognostic variables, archived at a 6-hour temporal resolution. The horizontal and vertical grid specifications remained unchanged throughout the simulations for consistency.

2.2 Observation Datasets

Multiple global low cloud datasets exist from several passive sensing satellites, such as the International Satellite Cloud Climatology Project (ISCCP). Although passive sensing provides useful information on low clouds horizontally, they are limited in their ability to detect multi-layer or deep clouds. Thus, it has difficulty in detecting cloud top height and vertical structure. In contrast to ISCCP, the CloudSat and Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation (CALIPSO) satellites provide vertical profile data. This capability arises from the complementary strengths of their instrumentation: the Cloud Profiling Radar (CPR) on CloudSat excels at identifying dense hydrometeor layers with high optical thickness, while the CALIPSO lidar effectively detects tenuous cloud layers often undetectable by the CPR. In this study, we use CloudSat data from 2006 to 2020, excluding the period in 2011 when a severe anomaly occurred. For other meteorological data, we use the latest ERA5 reanalysis from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). The observed all-sky and clear-sky radiative fluxes at the top of the atmosphere (TOA) are from the Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES).

Table 1. Observation data and source

Variable	Data Source
Cloud	CloudSat- Calipso
Radiation flux	CERES
Sea Surface Temperature	ERA5
Temperature	ERA5

Vertical Velocity	ERA5
Relative Humidity	ERA5

2.3 Cloud Controlling Factors

These studies operate on the premise that tropical low-cloud properties governing radiative fluxes (including low-cloud fraction and shortwave cloud-radiative effects) exhibit anomalies ΔC describable through a first order linear Taylor expansion around the climatology in their controlling factors $x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$:

$$\Delta C = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial C(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\partial x_i} \Delta x_i + \text{high order terms} \quad (1)$$

where Δx_i 's represent anomalies of controlling factors. Equation (1) defines the partial derivative $\partial C/\partial x_i$ as quantifying low-cloud sensitivity to controlling factors, maintaining temporal invariance across scales. This sensitivity persists whether anomalies manifest over inter-annual, decadal, centennial, or weekly periods, provided durations exceed ~ 2 -3 days - the maximum adjustment period for marine boundary layer clouds to equilibrate with exogenous forcings (Bretherton, 1993; Schubert et al., 1979). Temporal averaging diminishes but cannot fully eliminate cloud-controlling factor disequilibria.

Table 2 details the primary factors controlling tropical low clouds. For each factor, it provides the underlying reason for the cloud dependency and references a relevant observational or large-eddy simulation (LES) study. While substantial research backs each entry, the level of theoretical grounding and supporting evidence varies considerably among them. The connection linking stronger low cloud cover to increased inversion strength represents the most well-established relationship.

Table 2. Most important cloud controlling factors

Cloud controlling factor	Journal	Physical Meaning
Estimated Inversion	Wood &	The less mixing in inversion makes

Strength (EIS)	Bretherton, (2006)	boundary layer shallower, which cause more humid and more cloud.
Subsidence	Myers & Norris, (2013)	When subsidence reduced, the boundary layer will deeper, and more cloud.
Horizontal advection	Norris & Iacobellis, (2005)	The instability in the interface of surface and atmosphere will cause upward buoyancy flux which cause more cloud.
Free-Troposphere Humidity	Myers & Norris, (2016)	Higher free-tropospheric humidity causes less entrainment drying, which lead to more saturated in boundary layer and more cloud.
Downward longwave radiation	Christensen et al. (2013)	Less downward longwave radiation causes more cloud top radiative cooling, which drive more turbulence and more cloud.
Sea Surface Temperature	Qu et al., (2015)	More cloud to produce the entrainment rate for a less efficiency of entrainment when sea surface temperature is colder.
Surface Wind Speed	Brueck et al. (2015)	When surface wind increasing, the wind shear mixing increasing and cause more latent heat flux thus more cloud.

Determining the precise contribution of individual factors from observations can be challenging due to covarying relationships, such as that between free-tropospheric relative humidity and downward longwave radiation. While models can isolate these effects, observational disentanglement is often inconclusive. Furthermore, consistent large-scale observational data for some controlling factors is sometimes lacking.

Table 2 likely includes all major cloud-controlling factors relevant to large-scale processes. This comprehensiveness stems from its coverage of the principal external variables found in the boundary layer's energy and moisture budget equations (Stevens & Brenguier, 2009). Nevertheless, the list might omit some recognized elements (e.g., aerosol effects) or unidentified factors, though these are expected to play only a secondary role in the feedback response of tropical low clouds to climate warming.

In this study, we only consider most common used four CCF, which shown in

Figure 1. Generally, when relative humidity at 700 hPa get higher, subsidence weaker (Vertical velocity used in this study), Estimated inversion strength (EIS) stronger, sea surface temperature (SST) colder, the low cloud will increase and vice versa.

Figure 1. Schematic summary of how low-level clouds respond to changes in each large-scale meteorological cloud-controlling factor. (From Scott et al., 2020)

2.4 Low Cloud Decomposition

The low cloud fraction (LCF) changes with surface temperature (T_s) change can use first order Taylor expansion to represent as

$$\frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \sum_i \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF_i} \frac{dCCF_i}{dT_s} \quad (2)$$

where CCF means cloud controlling factors. We considered four most important CCFs used in this study, the LCF changes with surface temperature as

$$\frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial EIS} \frac{dEIS}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial RH_{700}} \frac{dRH_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial OMEGA_{700}} \frac{dOMGEA_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial SST} \frac{dSST}{dT_s}$$

where RH_{700} means relative humidity at 700 hPa, $OMGEA_{700}$ means vertical velocity at 700 hPa. The mult-linear regression method is used to calculate the first term (the partial derivatives) of the right side of formula 2. And linear regression method to

calculate the second term, how CCFs vary in response to warming.

3 CESM2 Result Validation

This study we focused on the cloud fraction. To valid the CESM2 output, we compare the climatological distributions of cloud and cloud radiative effect. Clouds display considerable variation in form and exhibit significant changes over both space and time. ISCCP classifies cloud types primarily using two parameters: the pressure at top and their optical depth (see Figure 2). Clouds with tops found at pressures less than 440 hPa are classified as high-level; this category comprises cirrus, cirrostratus, and deep convective clouds, spanning a wide range of optical thickness values. Mid-level clouds are identified by top pressures ranging from 440 hPa to 680 hPa and include types such as altocumulus, altostratus, and nimbostratus. Low-level clouds possess tops above 680 hPa pressure and consist of cumulus, stratocumulus, and stratus varieties.

Figure 2. Cloud types defined by the International Satellite Cloud Climatology Project (ISCCP), <https://isccp.giss.nasa.gov/cloudtypes.html> (From Su & Du, 2024).

Based on ISCCP multi-satellite data collected from 1984 to 2014, Figure 3 (e-h) depicts the climatological patterns of cloud coverage (total, high, mid, and low). Low clouds show a strong concentration over the eastern sections of ocean basins and

adjacent to western continental coastlines, globally averaging 28%. Mid-level (21% global mean) and high-level (13% global mean) clouds are prevalent over specific regions: the western Pacific, eastern Indian Ocean, the equatorial Pacific and Atlantic (within the Inter-tropical Convergence Zone or ITCZ), central Africa, South America, and mid-latitude storm tracks. The overall global average for total cloud cover during this period is approximately 33%. The CESM2 simulation is shown in Figure 3 (a-d), compare to ISCCP, the global mean is very close except for high clouds. For distribution, CESM2 overestimate the low clouds in polar region.

Figure 3. Average annual mean cloud amount from CESM2 from 1986 to 2000 and from the ISCCP from 1984 to 2014, (a and e) Low clouds; (b and f) Middle clouds; (c and g) High clouds; (d and h) All clouds.

Cloud Radiative Effects (CREs) measure the net radiative forcing exerted by clouds on the Earth's climate system. They are determined by calculating the difference between the top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiative fluxes under all-sky conditions and those under clear-sky conditions. A positive CRE value denotes a net warming influence on the atmosphere, while a negative CRE signifies net cooling. The shortwave CRE (SW CRE), responsible for cooling, generally increases with higher cloud optical depth. Conversely, the longwave CRE (LW CRE), which produces warming, typically becomes stronger as cloud top pressure decreases (meaning clouds are at higher altitudes). Consequently, optically dense low-level clouds mainly induce significant

SW cooling, while high-altitude, optically thin clouds predominantly contribute to LW warming.

Figure 4 (d-f) displays the spatial patterns of top-of-atmosphere (TOA) shortwave (SW CRE), longwave (LW CRE), and net cloud radiative effects derived from Clouds and Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) data averaged across March 2000 to November 2023. The most intense SW cooling occurs predominantly across the Inter-tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), western Pacific warm pool, eastern Indian Ocean, western continental coastal zones, the Southern Ocean, and mid-latitude storm tracks in both Pacific and Atlantic basins. Significant LW warming is concentrated over the ITCZ, western Pacific, eastern Indian Ocean, and equatorial landmasses of Africa and South America. Global mean values reveal clouds exert a SW cooling of -46 W/m^2 and LW warming of $+28 \text{ W/m}^2$, resulting in a net radiative cooling effect of -18 W/m^2 . The CESM2 simulation is shown in Figure 4 (a-c), compare to CERES, climatological mean of shortwave is overestimated, longwave is underestimated, thus net cloud radiative effect is overestimated. Although there are some magnitude differences between CESM2 and observation, the pattern of cloud and CRE are same, we can use this simulation to further investigation.

Figure 4. Climatological distributions of longwave, shortwave, and net cloud radiative effects based on CESM2 from 1986 to 2000 and CERES observations from March 2000 to November 2023.

4 Positive or negative low cloud feedback inferred from seasonality?

Many studies suggest positive low-cloud feedback in climate projections (Zelinka et al., 2020). This positive feedback arises primarily from the reduction in low cloud cover under surface warming, which enhances solar absorption at the surface and thereby amplifies the initial warming. However, the magnitude of this cloud response varies substantially across general circulation models, constituting a major source of uncertainty in climate sensitivity estimates. Although the overall sign of the feedback is consistently positive in most models, the underlying physical mechanisms—particularly the processes responsible for low-cloud reduction—remain inadequately understood and represent a critical research challenge (Boucher et al., 2014; Forster et al., 2023).

A key point of contention lies in the seasonal cycle of extratropical low cloud fraction (ELCF). Jiang et al. (2023) defined low cloud fraction (LCF) as the maximum overlap below 700 hPa. They found that ELCF shows a significant seasonal cycle peaking in winter in both high-ECS models and CloudSat-CALIPSO observations. In contrast, low-ECS models exhibit a weaker cycle that peaks in summer. This phasing aligns with positive low-cloud feedback in the seasonal cycle. Given the strong positive relationship between the seasonal sensitivity of ELCF to temperature ($dELCF/dT_s$) and ECS itself, the seasonal cycle of ELCF has been proposed as an emergent constraint (Zhai et al., 2015), with CloudSat-CALIPSO observations constraining ECS near 4.4 K—closer to the high-ECS models.

However, Furtado et al. (2023), using the ISCCP definition (cloud top below 680 hPa), found that low clouds in the extratropical oceans (particularly the Northwest

Pacific Oyashio region) peak in summer. Their analysis with the HadGEM3 PPE large ensemble suggested that this phasing is associated with stronger negative low-cloud feedback in the mid-latitudes, leading to an overestimation of ECS. Thus, both studies used the seasonal cycle of extratropical low clouds to constrain ECS but arrived at contradictory conclusions. We now perform a detailed analysis to resolve this discrepancy.

4.1 New cloud classification method based on cloud top height

To investigate the differing seasonal cycles of ELCF in high- and low-ECS models, Jiang et al. (2023) employed an Empirical Orthogonal Function (EOF) analysis to classify clouds into three regimes: High-top, Mid-top, and Low-top. To resolve the discrepancy arising from differing low-cloud definitions in the literature, we develop a physically based classification scheme using cloud-top height. Based on this criterion, we categorize clouds into three types (illustrated in Figure 5):

1. Multi-layer clouds (MLC): defined by a cloud top above 700 hPa, these typically include deep convective systems or cirrus with underlying low clouds.
2. Upper boundary-layer clouds (UBC): with a cloud top between 850 and 700 hPa, these are generally composed of thicker cumulus clouds.
3. Lower boundary-layer clouds (LBC): with a cloud top at or below 850 hPa, these are primarily stratocumulus clouds formed under boundary-layer inversions.

The selection of 700 hPa and 850 hPa as thresholds is physically justified: 850 hPa represents the boundary between the atmospheric boundary layer and free atmosphere, while 700 hPa is a critical level governing lower boundary-layer stability. Using this three-type framework, we examine the cause of the discrepancy.

Figure 5. Schematic of the three cloud types (Multi-layer Cloud; Upper Boundary Layer Cloud; Lower Boundary Layer Cloud)

4.2 The distribution of three types of cloud

As shown in Table 3, the MLC fraction shows the largest bias and a key model-observation discrepancy, with high-ECS models simulating larger values and low-ECS models simulating smaller ones. Among the three cloud types in observations, Multi-Layer Clouds (MLC, 17%) are the most dominant, followed by Upper Boundary-layer Clouds (UBC, 6.1%), with Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC, 4.4%) being the least prevalent. Besides, most models underestimate the UBC. However, all models perform well in simulating the LBC, which are controlled by the boundary layer inversion. Given our focus on seasonal cloud cycles and for better consistency with previous research, we select the MPI-ESM1 and CESM2 models for detailed analysis to facilitate comparison with the studies by Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023).

Table 3. Percentage of three clouds on both observation and models

	CloudSat	NorESM ECS=2.5K	MPI-ESM ECS=2.98K	CNRM-ESM ECS=4.76K	CNRM-CM ECS=4.83K	CESM2 ECS=5.16K	TaiESM ECS=5.34K	HadGEM3 ECS=5.55K
MLC	17.0%	17.1%	11.3%	13.6%	13.6%	19.3%	19.1%	20.0%
UBC	6.1%	5.6%	1.7%	1.4%	1.4%	7.5%	1.6%	1.9%
LBC	4.4%	3.1%	4.2%	4.1%	4.1%	5.2%	3.5%	3.8%

Based on Table 3, we first analyze the mean-state cloud amount for the three cloud types. Figure 6 then compares the horizontal distributions of the three cloud types between the selected models and observations. In the observations (Figures 6a, 6d, 6g), MLC is predominantly found in the ITCZ and extratropical storm-track regions. Both UBC and LBC are concentrated in the subtropical low-cloud regimes along eastern ocean boundaries. Notably, while CESM2 captures the overall UBC mean-state amount, its spatial distribution (Figure 6f) shows significant discrepancies from the observations (Figure 6d). This bias is particularly pronounced in the subtropics.

Figure 6. Horizontal distribution of three types of low clouds a)-c) Multi-Layer Cloud; d)-f) Upper Boundary Layer Cloud; g)-i) Lower Boundary Layer Cloud for CloudSat, MPI-ESM and CESM2, respectively.

4.3 The seasonal cycle of three types of clouds

To investigate the seasonal cycles of different cloud regimes, Figure 7 presents the observed seasonal variations of all three cloud types and the vertical structure at 40°N. It is clear that MLC and UBC exhibit a winter-maximum and summer-minimum cycle. In contrast, LBC shows an opposite pattern, with a minimum in winter and a maximum

in summer. These seasonal oscillations are primarily confined to extratropical regions. The opposing phases between boundary-layer clouds (LBC) and deeper cloud systems (MLC/UBC) suggest that distinct physical mechanisms control their seasonal behaviors.

Figure 7. Observed seasonal variations for different cloud types. Top row: Zonal-mean cloud fraction for (a) Multi-Layer, (b) Upper Boundary Layer, and (c) Lower Boundary Layer Clouds. Bottom row: Vertical structure at 40°N for (d) Multi-Layer, (e) Upper Boundary Layer, and (f) Lower Boundary Layer Clouds for CloudSat-CALIPSO from 2006 to 2011.

Figure 8 presents the observed seasonal variation of low clouds, depicted as the monthly zonal mean after subtracting the annual mean. The figure clearly shows that both MLC and UBC peak in winter in the extratropics, while LBC peaks in summer. From the perspective of vertical structure, the maximum overlap of MLC below 700 hPa is more pronounced in winter than in summer. However, within the lower boundary layer (from 900 hPa to the surface), MLC cover remains greater in summer. Since the seasonal cycle in the middle and upper layers is more pronounced, the maximum overlap of MLC is higher in winter. In contrast, for both UBC and LBC, the vertical structure is consistent with the results derived from the maximum overlap assumption.

Figure 8. Observed seasonal variations for different cloud types. Top row: Zonal-mean cloud fraction for (a) Multi-Layer, (b) Upper Boundary Layer, and (c) Lower Boundary Layer Clouds. Bottom row: Vertical structure at 40°N for (d) Multi-Layer, (e) Upper Boundary Layer, and (f) Lower Boundary Layer Clouds for CloudSat-CALIPSO from 2006 to 2011 with annual mean removed, respectively

To reconcile the differences between Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023), Figure 9 compares the seasonal variations of low clouds in both observations and models, applying the same definition as Jiang et al. (2023) (maximum overlapping cloud fraction below 700 hPa). Consistent with the findings of Jiang et al. (2023), observations and high-ECS models exhibit winter peaks, while low-ECS models show summer peaks. From a vertical structure perspective, although the seasonal cycles of upper boundary-layer clouds are consistent across models, the relative variation magnitude between lower and upper boundary-layer clouds determines the models' seasonal cycle characteristics. In the MPI model, for instance, lower boundary-layer clouds dominate, leading to a summer peak. Therefore, we conducted separate analyses for each of the three cloud types across the models.

Figure 9. Observed and modeled seasonal cycle of total LCF (defined by Jiang et al., 2023) Top row: Zonal-mean cloud fraction respective annual mean removed for a) CloudSat; b) MPI-ESM; c) CESM2. Bottom row: Vertical structure at 40°N for d) CloudSat; e) MPI-ESM; f) CESM2.

Among the three cloud types, MLC has the highest mean amount. Both CloudSat observations and CESM2 show a pronounced enhancement during winter in the upper troposphere. In contrast, the MPI model not only underestimates the mean cloud amount but also fails to accurately capture the seasonal cycle. The second row of panels further reveals that while the models generally overestimate low-level cloud cover in summer, CESM2 is dominated by upper-level clouds during this season. In contrast, the MPI model remains dominated by low-level clouds.

Figure 10. Seasonal cycle of the MLC vertical structure from observations (CloudSat) and models (MPI-ESM, CESM2) at 40°N. Panels (a-c) present the actual values, and panels (d-f) show the values with the annual mean removed.

Similar to MLC, Upper Boundary-layer Clouds (UBC) also peak in winter. CESM2 better reproduces the observed UBC patterns than the MPI model. In both cloud fraction and seasonal cycle, CESM2 demonstrates a significantly better representation than MPI-ESM. Furthermore, although CESM2 captures the observed seasonal cycle, its simulated vertical structure indicates that the cloud tops and bases of UBC—which exhibit distinct seasonal variations—are situated slightly higher than in the CloudSat observations.

Figure 11. Seasonal cycle of the UBC vertical structure from observations (CloudSat) and models (MPI-ESM, CESM2) at 40°N. Panels (a-c) present the actual values, and panels (d-f) show the values with the annual mean removed.

Contrary to the typical response of low clouds, Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC) increase with rising surface temperatures, leading to a summer maximum. Both models successfully capture this observed LBC seasonality. However, in the vertical structure, CESM2 simulates LBC with a cloud top higher than observed.

Figure 12. Seasonal cycle of the LBC vertical structure from observations (CloudSat) and models (MPI-ESM, CESM2) at 40°N. Panels (a-c) present the actual values, and panels (d-f) show the values with the annual mean removed.

4.4 Cloud-type-dependent biases causes discrepancy

The analysis of seasonal cycles and vertical structures across the three cloud types in both models and observations provides key insights. To directly address the discrepant findings between Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023), we compare the seasonal cycles of low clouds as defined by each study in both models and observations. The Jiang et al. (2023) definition (maximum overlap below 700 hPa), which essentially combines MLC, UBC, and LBC (Figure 13), is dominated by MLC due to its predominant fraction. Consequently, this composite low-cloud amount

exhibits a winter maximum.

Figure 13. Seasonal cycle of the LCF (maximum overlap below 700hPa) from observations (a) CloudSat and models (b) MPI-ESM, c) CESM2) with the annual mean removed.

In contrast, Furtado et al. (2023) focused on UBC + LBC (shown in Figure 14). Due to the model's underestimation of UBC, this combination is primarily dominated by LBC, thereby resulting in a summer maximum.

Figure 14. Seasonal cycle of the LCF (UBC + LBC; cloud top below 700hPa) from observations (a) CloudSat and models (b) MPI-ESM, c) CESM2) with the annual mean removed.

To ensure a fair comparison between the sun-synchronous polar-orbiting CloudSat (which observes at fixed local times) and the geostationary satellites used by ISCCP, we restricted the ISCCP data to match CloudSat's local overpass times. A notable summer peak appears in the ISCCP data but is absent in CloudSat observations. This discrepancy is likely attributable to limitations in ISCCP's cloud-type discrimination at high latitudes (Wang et al., 2016). As shown in Figure 16, ISCCP's accuracy in identifying single-layer low-level clouds is significantly reduced in winter, whereas its rate of misclassifying multilayered clouds as low-level clouds remains nearly constant throughout the year.

The CLARA dataset, which builds upon ISCCP, addresses this issue of low-cloud

underestimation (often caused by obscuring high-level thin clouds) by applying a CALIPSO-informed Naïve Bayesian classification. The seasonal cycle in CLARA also exhibits a winter maximum and summer minimum at mid-latitudes, consistent with CloudSat observations. This agreement underscores that retrieving low clouds from passive infrared brightness temperatures alone can introduce significant errors, representing a key reason for the divergent conclusions between the two studies.

Figure 15. Seasonal cycle of the LCF (UBC + LBC; cloud top below 700hPa from a) CloudSat and b) MPI-ESM (fixed local times same as CloudSat) c) CLARA-A3.

Figure 16. Assessment of ISCCP low-cloud accuracy against CloudSat-CALIPSO for (a) single-layer low clouds and (b) multi-layer clouds (low clouds beneath higher cloud layers).

In conclusion, the divergent conclusions between Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al. (2023) stem from two main factors. First, the studies examined distinct categories of low clouds. Second, the datasets used in each study exhibit markedly different seasonal cycles. Additionally, the emergent constraint approach relies on the critical assumption that interannual variability can serve as a proxy for long-term climate change. However, due to observational limitations, this study can only assess the robustness of the seasonal-to-interannual relationship across the three cloud regimes. To further investigate this assumption, we also examine the responses of the three cloud

types across seasonal, interannual, and long-term timescales

5 How three types of clouds change over different time scale?

For MLC and UBC, the patterns of seasonal and interannual variation are the same. In contrast, LBC exhibits significant differences across these timescales. To explore this further, we analyzed the responses of the three cloud regimes to surface temperature changes across both seasonal and interannual scales.

Figure 17. Change in low clouds across timescales (Summer – Winter for seasonal timescale; Warm year – Cold year for inter-annual timescale). Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for MLC, UBC, and LBC, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the same cloud types.

The left-hand side (LHS) term is equal to the sum of the products of the four right-hand side (RHS) terms.

$$\frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial EIS} \frac{dEIS}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial RH_{700}} \frac{dRH_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial OMEGA_{700}} \frac{dOMGEA_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial SST} \frac{dSST}{dT_s}$$

5.1 Multi-Layer Cloud

For MLC, the spatial patterns of seasonal and interannual variability share the same sign, despite differences in magnitude. However, significant inter-model disparities exist—the MPI model even shows responses of opposite sign compared to observations in extratropical regions. This bias in the MPI model directly explains its anomalous summer peak in low-cloud fraction. Additionally, both MPI and CESM2 exhibit biases on interannual timescales.

Figure 18. Sensitivity of MLC to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

5.2 Upper Boundary-layer Cloud

For Upper Boundary-layer Clouds (UBC), the cloud sensitivity to surface temperature remains consistent across both seasonal and interannual timescales. CESM2 performs well in simulating UBC sensitivity to T_{as} on interannual timescales but exhibits a spatial pattern opposite to observations in extratropical regions on seasonal timescales. In contrast, the MPI model shows significant deviations from observations at both timescales.

Figure 19. Sensitivity of UBC to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

5.3 Lower Boundary-layer Cloud

In contrast to MLC and UBC, Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC) exhibit timescale-dependent responses to T_{as} , although the inter-model spread is small. It is noteworthy that CESM2's simulation is opposite to observations in the extratropical regions of the Southern Hemisphere.

Figure 20. Sensitivity of LBC to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

6 How well four CCFs explain the cloud sensitivities to Tas on two timescales?

To identify the physical processes driving inter-model spread in cloud simulations across timescales, we analyzed four key cloud-controlling factors (CCFs). We first evaluated the effectiveness of these CCFs in capturing cloud sensitivity to surface air temperature (Tas) by calculating the regression residuals (ε ; Eq. 3). The Root Mean Square Errors (RMSE) of the CCF regressions for the three cloud types across both timescales are summarized in Table 4.

$$\sum \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF_i} \frac{\partial CCF_i}{\partial T_s} - \frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Overall, RMSE values are consistently lower at the seasonal scale than at the interannual scale across all cloud types, for both models and observations. For observations, LBC shows the lowest RMSE (seasonal: 0.0021; interannual: 0.007), followed by UBC (seasonal: 0.0045; interannual: 0.0129), and then MLC (seasonal: 0.0082; interannual: 0.0208). In the MPI model, UBC has the smallest RMSE (seasonal: 0.0005; interannual: 0.0008), followed by MLC (seasonal: 0.0011; interannual: 0.0016), with LBC exhibiting the largest error (seasonal: 0.0021; interannual: 0.0016). In contrast, CESM2 shows the largest RMSE for UBC (seasonal: 0.0032; interannual: 0.0057) and the smallest for LBC (seasonal: 0.0018; interannual: 0.0034). Following the RMSE analysis, we further examined the spatial distribution of the residuals for each model and cloud type.

Table 4. RMSE for three types of cloud on two timescales by using CCFs method

CloudSat		MPI-ESM		CESM2	
		ECS=2.98K		ECS=5.16K	
Seasonal	Inter-annual	Seasonal	Inter-annual	Seasonal	Inter-annual

MLC	0.0082	0.0208	0.0011	0.0016	0.0029	0.0044
UBC	0.0045	0.0129	0.0005	0.0008	0.0032	0.0057
LBC	0.0021	0.0070	0.0021	0.0031	0.0018	0.0034

6.1 Multi-Layer Cloud

The residuals for MLC are shown in Figure 21. CloudSat observations indicate high sensitivity of MLC to T_{as} in the equatorial region at both timescales. Both the MPI and CESM2 models underestimate this sensitivity in the same region. In extratropical regions, however, the models and observations all exhibit relatively small residuals, except for CloudSat at the interannual scale, which shows larger residuals, indicating that additional variability is not captured by the considered CCFs.

Figure 21. Residuals (time-mean bias) of the CCF regression for MLC against T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the residuals at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding residuals at the inter-annual timescale for the observation and MPI-ESM and CESM2 models.

6.2 Upper Boundary Layer Cloud

For UBC, the residuals in the MPI model are notably small, which can be attributed to its severe underestimation of the UBC mean state. CloudSat results indicate high sensitivity of UBC to T_{as} . CESM2 shows comparable sensitivity, except for lower

values in the subtropical region. For both models and observations, the CCF-derived residuals are substantially smaller at the seasonal than at the interannual timescale.

Figure 22. Residuals (time-mean bias) of the CCF regression for UBC against T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the residuals at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding residuals at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

6.3 Lower Boundary Layer Cloud

For LBC, both models and observations exhibit relatively small residuals. CloudSat shows slightly larger residuals at the interannual than at the seasonal timescale. The MPI model shows some overestimation in the eastern Pacific low-cloud regimes.

Figure 23. Residuals (time-mean bias) of the CCF regression for LBC against T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the residuals at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding residuals at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7 How three types of clouds are affected by CCFs on two timescales

7.1 LCF sensitivities to CCFs (Local Effect)

The first term represents the cloud sensitivity to CCFs, which is predominantly influenced by local factors. Since each model employs its own cloud parameterization scheme, this term is primarily responsible for the inter-model spread. For MLC, vertical velocity at 700 hPa is the primary driver of the inter-model spread. For UBC, SST and EIS are the main contributors to the inter-model spread. For LBC, SST and EIS are also the main contributors to the inter-model spread.

7.1.1 Sea surface temperature (SST) for MLC

SST is the most influential CCF for MLC. In observations, the sensitivity of MLC to SST is negative across most regions globally at both seasonal and interannual timescales. This implies that MLC would decrease under global warming. In models,

both high-ECS and low-ECS models exhibit consistency with observations at the seasonal timescale. However, deviations from observations arise at the interannual timescale: while errors are relatively small in subtropical (low-latitude) regions, the linear regression coefficient between MLC and SST becomes positive in high-latitude regions.

Figure 24. Sensitivity of MLC to SST across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.2 Estimated inversion strength (EIS) for MLC

EIS is also a highly influential CCF for MLC. In observations, the sensitivity of MLC to EIS differs substantially between seasonal and interannual timescales. At the seasonal timescale, the sensitivity is positive in both tropical and extratropical regions, while the relationship is weak or insignificant in key low-cloud regimes (e.g., the subtropical eastern Pacific). In contrast, at the interannual timescale, the sensitivity becomes negative in most regions, except over the eastern Pacific and parts of the Southern Hemisphere extratropics, where it remains positive. As for the models, both MPI-ESM and CESM2 capture the spatial pattern well at seasonal timescale. However, they fail to reproduce the observed scale-dependent contrast, simulating similar sensitivity patterns across timescales, which differs from the observations at the

interannual timescale.

Figure 25. Sensitivity of MLC to EIS across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.3 Relative humidity at 700 hPa for MLC

The sensitivity of MLC to RH700 exhibits consistent spatial patterns across both observational data and model simulations, as well as between different timescales. Positive sensitivity is found in tropical and extratropical regions, while the relationship is weak or insignificant elsewhere. This underscores the crucial role of RH700 in influencing MLC.

Figure 26. Sensitivity of MLC to relative humidity at 700 hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show

the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.4 Vertical velocity at 700 hPa for MLC

Although the models show consistent patterns across timescales, which align with observations, MPI fails to accurately simulate the relationship between subtropical MLC and OMEGA700 at both seasonal and interannual timescales. OMEGA also plays a critical role in MLC formation, stronger upward motion at 700 hPa corresponds to greater MLC occurrence.

Figure 27. Sensitivity of MLC to vertical velocity at 700 hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.5 Sea surface temperature (SST) for UBC

For UBC, SST also exerts the dominant influence. In observations, the spatial patterns of UBC sensitivity to SST are generally similar between seasonal and interannual timescales, except near the eastern Pacific western coast, where the relationship shifts from positive at the seasonal scale to negative at the interannual scale.

Due to MPI's substantial underestimation of UBC, its simulated sensitivity patterns are incorrect at both timescales. In contrast, CESM2 shows notable errors in tropical regions, where it simulates an increase in UBC with increasing SST across both timescales.

Figure 28. Sensitivity of UBC to SST across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.6 Estimated inversion strength (EIS) for UBC

The spatial patterns of UBC sensitivity to EIS in CESM2 are consistent with observations at both seasonal and interannual timescales. The sensitivity is negative in extratropical regions, while it is positive across most subtropical areas—except in the warm pool region, where it turns negative. In contrast, MPI only captures the subtropical pattern correctly and likewise shows consistent sensitivity patterns across both timescales.

Figure 29. Sensitivity of UBC to EIS across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.7 Relative humidity at 700 hPa for UBC

For Relative humidity at 700 hPa, there is a notable inter-model spread in the simulated sensitivity of UBC. In CESM2, the spatial pattern is consistent across both timescales and agrees well with observations: sensitivity is positive in the eastern Pacific tropical cold tongue region and negative in extratropical regions. In contrast, MPI shows similar patterns across timescales but is inconsistent with observations; the sensitivity is near-zero in most regions, except for positive values in the eastern Pacific cold tongue tropical area.

Figure 30. Sensitivity of UBC to relative humidity at 700hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.8 Vertical velocity at 700 hPa for UBC

The sensitivity of UBC to vertical velocity at 700 hPa shows consistent patterns across timescales in both observations and models. However, the simulated patterns in both models deviate from observations. Observations indicate a positive sensitivity in all regions except the tropical region. MPI fails to capture the positive relationship along the eastern Pacific low cloud regime, while CESM2 incorrectly simulates a negative sensitivity in both subtropical and extratropical regions.

Figure 31. Sensitivity of UBC to vertical velocity at 700hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.9 Sea surface temperature (SST) for LBC

The sensitivity of LBC to SST shows inconsistencies between the two timescales in the Northern Hemisphere extratropical regions. The spatial patterns in CESM2 are similar to observations at both timescales: showing positive sensitivity in extratropical regions and negative sensitivity in subtropical regions at the seasonal timescale, while the sensitivity also becomes negative in extratropical regions at the interannual timescale. In contrast, MPI erroneously simulates positive sensitivity in subtropical regions across both timescales.

Figure 32. Sensitivity of LBC to SST across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.10 Estimated inversion strength (EIS) for LBC

The sensitivity of LBC to EIS shows consistent spatial patterns across both timescales, characterized by negative values in subtropical regions and positive values in extratropical regions. However, neither MPI nor CESM2 successfully reproduces the observed negative values in subtropical regions at either timescale.

Figure 33. Sensitivity of LBC to EIS across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.11 Relative humidity at 700 hPa for LBC

The sensitivity of LBC to relative humidity at 700 hPa shows consistent spatial patterns in both MPI and CESM2 when compared to observations. These patterns remain stable across both timescales, characterized by a positive linear relationship in the subtropical low-cloud regime, weak or insignificant sensitivity in other subtropical regions, and a negative relationship in extratropical regions.

Figure 34. Sensitivity of LBC to relative humidity at 700hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.1.12 Vertical velocity at 700 hPa for LBC

The sensitivity of LBC to vertical velocity at 700 hPa shows generally low sensitivity, particularly in the subtropical regions. A positive linear relationship is observed only in the subtropical low-cloud regimes and extratropical regions, with consistent spatial patterns across both timescales. Both MPI and CESM2 simulate patterns that closely match the observations at both timescales.

Figure 35. Sensitivity of LBC to vertical velocity at 700hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.2 CCF sensitive to Tas (Remote Effect)

The second term on the right side of the equation is mainly controlled by large-scale circulation or teleconnections. This term is a key driver of the temporal variability, although inter-model differences are generally small except for vertical velocity. The most significant factor is EIS, whose sensitivity to Tas exhibits marked differences between seasonal and interannual timescales. Other variables also exhibit some differences between the two timescales.

7.2.1 Sea surface temperature (SST)

The spatial pattern of SST sensitivity to Tas across the tropical Pacific shows high values in the eastern Pacific and values approaching zero over the Western Pacific Warm Pool (WPWP) on both seasonal and interannual timescales. This can be explained within the Weak Temperature Gradient (WTG) theory. In the tropics, large-scale circulations act to minimize horizontal temperature gradients in the free atmosphere, which is effectively constrained by the SST in the warmest regions. In the WPWP, persistently high SSTs drive vigorous deep convection. The resulting energy is

primarily exported vertically via latent heating, driving large-scale remote circulations, while local cloud-radiative feedback significantly dampens the direct forcing of local T_{as} by SST. In contrast, the stable atmospheric boundary layer over the eastern Pacific suppresses deep convection, allowing SST variations to modulate T_{as} efficiently through direct local thermodynamic processes—namely sensible heat flux and longwave radiation.

Figure 36. Sensitivity of SST to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.2.2 Estimated inversion strength (EIS)

The spatial and scale-dependent relationship between Estimated Inversion Strength (EIS) and surface air temperature (T_{as}) arises from shifts in the dominant physical processes governing low-level atmospheric stability. On seasonal timescales, the sign of the linear coefficient reflects a contrast in causality: in the subtropics, intensified large-scale subsidence enhances EIS, which suppresses vertical mixing and surface warming, resulting in a negative correlation. On interannual timescales, this relationship becomes consistently negative across latitudes, as large-scale oceanic warming (e.g., during ENSO events) reduces lower-tropospheric static stability, thereby lowering EIS.

Figure 37. Sensitivity of EIS to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

According to the formula, EIS is nearly equals to lower troposphere stability (LTS)

$$EIS = LTS - \Gamma_m(Z_{700hpa} - Z_{LCL})$$

and LTS sensitive to T_{as} equals to potential temperature at 700 hPa sensitive to T_{as} minus one.

$$\frac{\partial LTS}{\partial T_s} = \frac{\partial \theta_{700hpa}}{\partial T_s} - 1$$

The distribution of LTS sensitive to T_{as} on two timescales are shown in Figure 38, the different increase speed of potential temperature at 700 hPa causes the change sign of sensitivity at extra-tropical region.

Figure 38. Sensitivity of LTS to T_{as} at a) the seasonal timescale b) at the inter-annual timescale for CESM2.

7.2.3 Relative humidity at 700 hPa

Figure 39 reveals distinct latitudinal patterns in the linear relationship between T_{as} and 700 hPa relative humidity across seasonal and interannual timescales. The spatial structure, which shows negative correlations near the equator and western Pacific warm pool, positive in the subtropics, and near-zero at high latitudes, stems from a shift in the dominant pathway through which T_{as} governs RH. In the warm pool regions, the thermodynamic pathway dominates: an increase in T_{as} induces an exponential rise in saturation vapor pressure, which outstrips any potential increase in specific humidity, thereby reducing RH and yielding a negative correlation. Conversely, in the subtropics, the dynamic pathway prevails: increased T_{as} enhances convective instability and ascent, effectively transporting moisture to the 700 hPa level. This moistening effect overcomes the increase in saturation vapor pressure, leading to a rise in RH and a positive correlation. At high latitudes, where saturation vapor pressure is intrinsically low, RH is primarily governed by moisture advection processes from local T_{as} variations, resulting in a negligible linear relationship.

Figure 39. Sensitivity of relative humidity at 700 hPa to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

7.2.4 Vertical velocity at 700 hPa

A stable positive correlation exists between 700-hPa vertical velocity (ω) and surface air temperature (Tas) over the equatorial and western Pacific warm pool regions on both seasonal and interannual timescales. In other regions, the values are always negative. There is a positive correlation between local surface temperature and the tropical-mean temperature. Consequently, the temperature in the western Pacific covaries with the tropical-mean temperature rather than with local SST. Since the tropical-mean temperature primarily reflects the El Niño signal, this results in the apparent paradox where higher temperature occurs in the western Pacific even when local SST is anomalously low.

Figure 40. Sensitivity of vertical velocity at 700 hPa to Tas across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

8 Conclusions and Discussions

This study introduces a cloud classification method based on cloud-top height, dividing low clouds into three distinct types: (1) multi-layer clouds (MLC, cloud top above 700 hPa); (2) upper boundary-layer clouds (UBC, cloud top between 850-700

hPa); and (3) lower boundary-layer clouds (LBC, cloud top capped at 850 hPa). This classification effectively disentangles the seasonal cycles of different cloud types, thereby resolving the apparent discrepancy between the conclusions of Jiang et al. (2023) and Furtado et al (2023). The main findings of this study are as follows:

1. Among the three cloud types, MLC is the most abundant, followed by UBC, with LBC being the least frequent. Both MLC and UBC exhibit a winter maximum and a summer minimum, whereas LBC shows the opposite pattern, with a summer maximum and a winter minimum. Models severely underestimate UBC. Simulated MLC amounts are biased, generally overestimated in high-climate-sensitivity models and underestimated in low-sensitivity models, while LBC is relatively well simulated. The low clouds referred to by Jiang et al (2023). consist of MLC + UBC + LBC. Since MLC dominates in abundance, the combined cloud amount exhibits a winter maximum and summer minimum. In contrast, Furtado et al (2023). focus on UBC + LBC. Due to the widespread model underestimation of UBC, this combination is dominated by LBC, resulting in a summer maximum and winter minimum. Furthermore, the use of ISCCP data by Furtado et al (2023). is problematic for this purpose, as ISCCP cannot adequately capture cloud vertical structure, leading to a substantial underestimation of low clouds in winter and consequently an erroneous seasonal cycle.

2. The three cloud types exhibit distinct patterns across different timescales and models. MLC and UBC show relatively consistent patterns between seasonal and inter-annual timescales but exhibit considerable inter-model spread. In contrast, LBC shows limited inter-model spread but displays significant differences between seasonal and inter-annual timescales. This indicates that LBC is not suitable for use as an emergent constraint.

3. The Cloud Controlling Factor (CCF) method effectively explains the behavior of the

three cloud types across timescales and the inter-model spread. The inter-model spread is primarily controlled by the sensitivity of clouds to the CCFs, while the variation across timescales is mainly governed by the sensitivity of the CCFs to Tas. The sensitivity signs of the three cloud types to the four CCFs are listed in Table 5. Among all CCFs, the sensitivity of clouds to SST is the strongest. For MLC, vertical velocity at 700 hPa is the primary driver of the inter-model spread. For UBC, SST and EIS are the main contributors to the inter-model spread. The inconsistency in LBC behavior between the two timescales is attributed to the differing responses of potential temperature at 700 hPa to Tas across timescales. This leads to differences in the sensitivity of EIS to Tas, which subsequently causes the inconsistency in LBC across timescales.

Table 5. Sensitivities sign of the three cloud types to the four CCFs

	MLC		UBC		LBC	
	Seasonal	Inter-Annual	Seasonal	Inter-Annual	Seasonal	Inter-Annual
SST ↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑	↓
EIS ↑	↑	-	↓	↓	↑	↑
ω_{700} ↑ (subsidence)	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	↑
RH700 ↑	↑	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓

Future investigations will quantify decadal variability and short-term, long-term trends across all three cloud regimes under the CCF framework. Concurrently, CERES-derived CRE exhibit coherent seasonal cycles (shown in Figure 40), prompting further analysis of radiation-modulation dynamics by each cloud type to better constrain model ECS spread.

Figure 41. Seasonal cycle of the a) shortwave, b) longwave, and c) net cloud radiative effect from CERES.

Furthermore, microphysical parameterization schemes significantly impact cloud representations (shown in Figure 42). We will therefore implement perturbed parameter ensemble (PPE) experiments to characterize microphysics-CCF interactions across cloud regimes, establishing an evidence-based parameterization optimization framework for climate model development.

Figure 42. Low cloud fraction in the CESM2 perturbed parameter ensemble (PPE): a) mean, b) standard deviation

Reference

Ad Hoc Study Group on Carbon Dioxide and Climate, Climate Research Board, Assembly of Mathematical and Physical Sciences, & National Research Council. (1979). *Carbon Dioxide and Climate: A Scientific Assessment* (p. 12181). National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/12181>

Andrews, T., Gregory, J. M., Webb, M. J., & Taylor, K. E. (2012). Forcing, feedbacks and climate sensitivity in CMIP5 coupled atmosphere-ocean climate models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *39*(9), 2012GL051607. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL051607>

Bogenschutz, P. A., Gettelman, A., Hannay, C., Larson, V. E., Neale, R. B., Craig, C., & Chen, C.-C. (2018). The path to CAM6: Coupled simulations with CAM5.4 and CAM5.5. *Geoscientific Model Development*, *11*(1), 235–255. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-235-2018>

Bony, S., & Dufresne, J. (2005). Marine boundary layer clouds at the heart of tropical cloud feedback uncertainties in climate models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *32*(20), 2005GL023851. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005GL023851>

Bretherton, C. S. (1993). Understanding Albrecht's Model of Trade Cumulus Cloud Fields. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, *50*(14), 2264–2283. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1993\)050<2264:UAMOTC>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1993)050<2264:UAMOTC>2.0.CO;2)

Brueck, M., Nuijens, L., & Stevens, B. (2015). On the Seasonal and Synoptic Time-Scale Variability of the North Atlantic Trade Wind Region and Its Low-Level Clouds. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, *72*(4), 1428–1446. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-14-0054.1>

Cess, R. D., Potter, G. L., Blanchet, J. P., Boer, G. J., Del Genio, A. D., Déqué, M., Dymnikov, V., Galin, V., Gates, W. L., Ghan, S. J., Kiehl, J. T., Lacis, A. A., Le Treut, H., Li, Z. -X., Liang, X. -Z., McAvaney, B. J., Meleshko, V. P., Mitchell, J. F. B., Morcrette, J. -J., ... Zhang, M. -H. (1990). Intercomparison and interpretation of climate feedback processes in 19 atmospheric general circulation models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *95*(D10), 16601–16615. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JD095iD10p16601>

Christensen, M. W., Carrió, G. G., Stephens, G. L., & Cotton, W. R. (2013). Radiative Impacts of Free-Tropospheric Clouds on the Properties of Marine Stratocumulus. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, *70*(10), 3102–3118. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-12-0287.1>

Frey, W. R., & Kay, J. E. (2018). The influence of extratropical cloud phase and amount feedbacks on climate sensitivity. *Climate Dynamics*, *50*(7–8), 3097–3116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-017-3796-5>

Furtado, K., Tsushima, Y., Field, P. R., Rostron, J., & Sexton, D. (2023). The Relationship Between the Present-Day Seasonal Cycles of Clouds in the Mid-Latitudes and Cloud-Radiative Feedback. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *50*(15), e2023GL103902. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL103902>

Gettelman, A., Bresch, D. N., Chen, C. C., Truesdale, J. E., & Bacmeister, J. T. (2018). Projections of future tropical cyclone damage with a high-resolution global climate model. *Climatic Change*, *146*(3–4), 575–585. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-017-1902-7>

Gettelman, A., & Sherwood, S. C. (2016). Processes Responsible for Cloud Feedback. *Current Climate Change Reports*, *2*(4), 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-016-0052-8>

Huang, B., Liu, C., Banzon, V., Freeman, E., Graham, G., Hankins, B., Smith, T., & Zhang, H.-M. (2021). Improvements of the Daily Optimum Interpolation Sea Surface Temperature (DOISST) Version 2.1. *Journal of Climate*, *34*(8), 2923–2939. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0166.1>

Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (Ed.). (2014). Clouds and Aerosols. In *Climate Change 2013 – The Physical Science Basis* (1st ed., pp. 571–658). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.016>

Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (Ipcc). (2023). *Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis: Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>

Jiang, X., Su, H., Jiang, J. H., Neelin, J. D., Wu, L., Tsushima, Y., & Elsaesser, G. (2023). Muted extratropical low cloud seasonal cycle is closely linked to underestimated climate sensitivity in models. *Nature Communications*, *14*(1), 5586. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41360-0>

Klein, S. A., Hall, A., Norris, J. R., & Pincus, R. (2017). Low-Cloud Feedbacks from Cloud-Controlling Factors: A Review. *Surveys in Geophysics*, 38(6), 1307–1329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-017-9433-3>

Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Eyring, V., Flato, G., Lamarque, J.-F., Stouffer, R. J., Taylor, K. E., & Schlund, M. (2020). Context for interpreting equilibrium climate sensitivity and transient climate response from the CMIP6 Earth system models. *Science Advances*, 6(26), eaba1981. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba1981>

Myers, T. A., & Norris, J. R. (2013). Observational Evidence That Enhanced Subsidence Reduces Subtropical Marine Boundary Layer Cloudiness. *Journal of Climate*, 26(19), 7507–7524. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00736.1>

Myers, T. A., & Norris, J. R. (2016). Reducing the uncertainty in subtropical cloud feedback. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 43(5), 2144–2148. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL067416>

Norris, J. R., & Iacobellis, S. F. (2005). North Pacific Cloud Feedbacks Inferred from Synoptic-Scale Dynamic and Thermodynamic Relationships. *Journal of Climate*, 18(22), 4862–4878. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI3558.1>

Qu, X., Hall, A., Klein, S. A., & DeAngelis, A. M. (2015). Positive tropical marine low-cloud cover feedback inferred from cloud-controlling factors. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42(18), 7767–7775. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL065627>

Rayner, N. A., Parker, D. E., Horton, E. B., Folland, C. K., Alexander, L. V., Rowell, D. P., Kent, E. C., & Kaplan, A. (2003). Global analyses of sea surface temperature, sea ice, and night marine air temperature since the late nineteenth century. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D14), 2002JD002670. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JD002670>

Schubert, W. H., Wakefield, J. S., Steiner, E. J., & Cox, S. K. (1979). Marine Stratocumulus Convection. part II: Horizontally Inhomogeneous Solutions. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 36(7), 1308–1324. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1979\)036<1308:MSCPIH>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1979)036<1308:MSCPIH>2.0.CO;2)

Scott, R. C., Myers, T. A., Norris, J. R., Zelinka, M. D., Klein, S. A., Sun, M., & Doelling, D. R. (2020). Observed Sensitivity of Low-Cloud Radiative Effects to Meteorological Perturbations over the Global Oceans. *Journal of Climate*, 33(18), 7717–7734. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-1028.1>

Sherwood, S. C., Webb, M. J., Annan, J. D., Armour, K. C., Forster, P. M., Hargreaves,

J. C., Hegerl, G., Klein, S. A., Marvel, K. D., Rohling, E. J., Watanabe, M., Andrews, T., Braconnot, P., Bretherton, C. S., Foster, G. L., Hausfather, Z., Von Der Heydt, A. S., Knutti, R., Mauritsen, T., ... Zelinka, M. D. (2020). An Assessment of Earth's Climate Sensitivity Using Multiple Lines of Evidence. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 58(4), e2019RG000678. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019RG000678>

Stephens, G. L. (2005). Cloud Feedbacks in the Climate System: A Critical Review. *Journal of Climate*, 18(2), 237–273. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-3243.1>

Stevens, B., & Brenguier, J.-L. (2009). Cloud-controlling Factors. In J. Heintzenberg & R. J. Charlson (Eds.), *Clouds in the Perturbed Climate System* (pp. 173–196). The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9780262012874.003.0008>

Su, H., & Du, S. (2024). Cloud Feedback. In *Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences* (p. B9780323960267000710). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-96026-7.00071-0>

Tan, I., Storelvmo, T., & Zelinka, M. D. (2016). Observational constraints on mixed-phase clouds imply higher climate sensitivity. *Science*, 352(6282), 224–227. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aad5300>

Wang, T., Fetzer, E. J., Wong, S., Kahn, B. H., & Yue, Q. (2016). Validation of MODIS cloud mask and multilayer flag using CloudSat-CALIPSO cloud profiles and a cross-reference of their cloud classifications. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 121(19). <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD025239>

Wood, R., & Bretherton, C. S. (2006). On the Relationship between Stratiform Low Cloud Cover and Lower-Tropospheric Stability. *Journal of Climate*, 19(24), 6425–6432. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI3988.1>

Zelinka, M. D., Myers, T. A., McCoy, D. T., Po-Chedley, S., Caldwell, P. M., Ceppi, P., Klein, S. A., & Taylor, K. E. (2020). Causes of Higher Climate Sensitivity in CMIP6 Models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(1), e2019GL085782. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL085782>

Zhai, C., Jiang, J. H., & Su, H. (2015). Long-term cloud change imprinted in seasonal cloud variation: More evidence of high climate sensitivity. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42(20), 8729–8737. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL065911>